
NEW MODERN TEACHING METHODS AND TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL DEPARTMENTS

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Annotation: Modernization of education focuses on developing students' communication skills in foreign languages, requiring the use of interactive teaching technologies and a collective nature of teaching. Training teachers with common interactive techniques allows students to consciously act and acquire experience and knowledge through their activities. Training highly qualified students is an urgent issue, especially for future teachers. Modern teaching methods and techniques are introduced to improve prospective teachers' proficiency in English. Language classes aim to improve language acquisition, and communicative language teaching emphasizes the need for students to be motivated. Technology creates different teaching and learning methods and techniques for teachers and students, making communication easier for both parties.

Key words: interactive techniques, problem-solving, gamification, communicative language, web-based decision.

The continuous improvement (reformation, modernization) of education is an integral part of the general trends of the development of education in a single European educational space. The task is to ensure the ultimate success of our graduates in the educational environment of the European Union. That is why our priority in modernizing education is the development of education, which allows everyone to become more educated, to find themselves in the profession for which they are ready and can be performed on a professional level. In the system of higher pedagogical education, much attention is paid to the formation of students' communication skills in a foreign language, which determines the need for the use of interactive teaching technologies, the collective nature of teaching. The use in training of teachers of common interactive techniques allows students to consciously act, to acquire experience, knowledge through their activities. This has made it possible to ensure the formation of future professionals, the development of the dynamics of their educational outcomes in the training of teaching subjects of the specialization of Pedagogical Education.

Training highly qualified students is always an urgent problem. An especially important issue is the education of future teachers, namely their professional outlook. The trouble is that future teachers are not satisfied with the degree of proficiency in

the discipline English, which is confirmed by the results of interviews, the results of the testing carried out during the classes, and the results of the exams. In order to improve prospective teachers of foreign language, modern teaching methods and techniques are introduced in the teaching process. It is the organization of interactive methods of learning that can ensure the best development of students: the ability to learn, analyze, and evaluate the results of their cognitive activity. In the learning process, psychological phenomena, cognitive processes, and features of personality development are revealed. Consequently, innovation in the process of education is of great importance; the main goal of improving teacher training is to form a holistic view of the educational process.

What is the function of a language class? The answer is simple. Its function is to improve language acquisition. The goal of choosing a particular teaching method should not be related to the possibility of presenting or not presenting a particular piece of information or topic to students. The goal of the class is not to present a list of 55 irregular verbs to be learned, but to use the attempt at mastering grammar and lexis with the aim of improving language acquisition. The main important reason for using only-English classes is that parents expect that after some years of study their children will be able to speak English effectively. After two or three years of study, not every pupil is able to ask for a glass of water without hesitation. Doing a class in English does not mean not knowing what to do. Methods and goals of instructions must be.

The method of communicative language teaching, in which one tries to make language itself central to the teaching and learning process, has brought about new ideas for English language instruction. One thing that it has accentuated is the need for students to be motivated. Methods in teaching are coming to emphasize more and more the need to motivate students, to encourage them to learn. More specifically, the objective is being set to motivate them to communicate. Do students in our Republic have to be encouraged to communicate? In English or in their native tongue? At the levels of English that we are teaching, they do. The reason is that generally we do not communicate with them and they do not communicate with us. After making exhortations through lectures, communication can be seen to decrease in the higher years of instruction.

In the novel methods, there are also some related to technology. A. D. Wilson and P. C. Miller remarked that a knowledge base is a new teaching method for globalizing business courses. They exemplify a web-based decision system that would help in its explication. They have done this to provide explanations and instructions, assignments, test solutions, and student grades as pre-class activities. With such preparatory activities, students can develop visualization skills in preparation for class. The core of this method involves taking problem-solving steps

in an electronic way, using hypertext links to connect sequentially with different learning using distinct physical senses, and using the semantic/visual aspect of the students' preferred learning style, using appropriate computer technology to deliver the problem-solving sequence. They state that students improved their problem-optical visualization. However, the intended impact of computer visualization has not yet been investigated.

According to the Cambridge dictionary, **gamification** is the process of adding games or game-like elements to something. It involves applying game design thinking to non-game applications to make them more fun and engaging. Gamification has become the most important aspect for the language learners. The language learner may grasp the game ideas easily as games are in great potential to give a theme-based and fun-oriented learning environment. Through gamification, teachers can incorporate educational content while allowing students to negotiate in complex tasks. The intention is neither to entertain nor even to engage, but to exploit powerful interactive dynamics to support learning and other activities needed by the curriculum. According to Gartner Inc, 70% of the Global 2000 organizations are expected to incorporate gamification in at least one area in the next few years.

In light of the international context of the diversified challenges to present-day humankind, the teaching of English to non-philological students of higher education ought to adopt the cognitivist and constructivist paradigms active nowadays in both the teaching of science and the approaches in dealing with art. The extension of project work, problem solving, the need for research for a given presentation or role playing should correspond to the requirements in any other field of higher education. The up-to-date qualifications of teaching languages for specific purposes ought to account for the ideal model that any top-quality non-philological institution of higher education ought to form.

The hardware of the educational institution ought to be accessible to the foreign-language institution (or department, faculty) and of the same quality with the rest of the facilities. The software ought to be challenging, stimulating, of different types according to the educational approaches, methods and techniques integrated into the normative documents of Uzbekistan Ministry of National Education. Starting from the idea that English is to be regarded as a non-philological tool language in sciences, in the social studies, or in the law and management departments (face-to-face or distance higher education), the qualifications in teaching the foreign language ought to be tailored to an international model. A master's degree in English methodologies and didactics specialized in a non-philological field ought to respond to the requirements of an academic education at a standard level.

Training and professional development focus on providing new insights and skills from various fields, as well as familiarizing faculty and staff with the necessary

tools, supports, and resources. Expert specialists in ELT, materials, methodological, and computer programs are often invited to demonstrate innovative teaching techniques to faculty members and provide computer exercises for educators. In the process of work seminars, group or individual consultation on teaching issues is held, interactive teaching sessions, team working groups, leaders, and teaching partners train each other. The purpose of such meetings is to educate educators who acquire new skills and engage in advanced teaching.

To develop interdisciplinary connections, professional development programs help faculty and staff determine what strategies will work in specialized educational areas. But not only the presence of modern educational methods, tricks, or various forms of organization of educational work guarantees success. Continuous teaching improvement should not result in revisiting traditional teaching methods or techniques: the goal of such work is to create new, more effective learning methods and to change content and goals as needed. Scheduled professional development points out the different, modern methods and techniques in teaching that faculty needs to apply in their teachings for successful cooperation. It is advisable to monitor and evaluate the current teaching format and content to fill in the gap of the major field content in comparison to other education fields.

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